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Support needs and post-adoption resources for adopted adults: a systematic review

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Abstract

Post-adoption services provide guidance to adoptive families concerning common and specific circumstances. Despite adoption is a lifelong experience, most of the post-adoption resources are oriented towards children, adolescents, and their adoptive parents. However, it is also necessary to focus on the demands and interventions with adult adoptees. The aim of this paper is to review adult adoptees' demands for post-adoption resources, applicants' characteristics, and resources offered to them. A systematic search was conducted in several databases, finding 40 studies that fulfilled the selection criteria (about adults, domestic/international adoptions, and published between 2005 and 2018). The included studies showed mainly three needs: contact with birth family, ethnic identity and birth culture, and psychological support. Additionally, adoptees who demand post-adoption resources are a heterogeneous group. This review collects structured programs focused on different topics: search for origins, attachment development, and professionals' training in adoption. In addition, we also found some specific post-adoption services and other tools, such as support groups or cultural events. Finally, adoptees also have access to other resources that are not specifically for them, like mental health services. The scarce existence of evidence-based interventions is an important weakness in this work. Recommendations for future research and practice are included.

Keywords: post-adoption, systematic review, support need, adult mental health care, adult adoptees.

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Introduction

The number of adoptions worldwide has varied over time, depending on the period and type of adoption. For instance, inter-country adoption increased until soon after 2000, and decreased from then on (Mignot, 2015). Meanwhile, professional intervention in adoption matters has evolved. Simultaneously, several demands have emerged, and a new map of services for adopted children and families has been established. Among them is post-adoption service, which, since 1993 in The Hague Convention (HCCH, 2018), has been proposed to include: support, search for origins, reports about birth country, and solutions to disruption.

Post-adoption services are offered to meet the needs, initially identified by families after initiating cohabitation. Due to respect for privacy, the post-adoption period is less visible, although support during this time is very important and demanded by adoptive families (ChildONEurope, 2007). Literature evidences some difficulties in adoptees and their families during the lifecycle. Research mainly explores the needs of adoptive families and children upon their arrival and subsequent adaptation during childhood (Bramlett *et al.*, 2007; Sánchez-Sandoval *et al.*, 2012; Zill and Bramlett, 2014; Fisher, 2015; Katzenstein *et al.*, 2016), as well as the identification of difficulties during adolescence, such an identity development (Passmore *et al.*, 2005; Mohanty, 2008; Grotevant *et al.*, 2017; Hu *et al.*, 2017) or psychological adjustment (Mohanty, 2008 Sánchez-Sandoval, 2015; Askeland *et al.*, 2017, 2018). Palacios (2007) highlights seven aspects related to the needs in childhood and adolescence: health, development, behavioural problems, attachment, loss, communication about adoption and search for origins. Post-adoption services provide support to adoptive families concerning common and specific issues.

Although adoption is a lifelong experience, most of the post-adoption resources are oriented towards children, adolescents and adoptive parents (Reilly and Platz, 2004; Dhami *et*

al., 2007; Stock *et al.*, 2016). Less is known about the demands and interventions with adults. In recent years, there has been growing interest in research of the adulthood stage (Rushton *et al.*, 2013; Dekker *et al.*, 2017; Sánchez-Sandoval and Melero, 2018). There are few published works about the needs of adult adoptees and the resources they use. According to Melero and Sánchez-Sandoval (2017), there is a gap in intervention and prevention because adults' needs are unknown.

Trying to address this situation, the main purpose of this work is to perform a systematic review of adult adoptees' needs and the formal and informal resources provided to them. The aims are to: (1) identify adult adoptees' demands of post-adoption resources, (2) study the sociodemographic and psychological characteristics of adult adoptees who use formal or informal post-adoption resources, and (3) describe and organise post-adoption resources and services offered to adult adoptees.

Methodology

For this systematic review, we implemented the suggestions of the PRISMA Group (2009). This evidence-based method includes different aspects about the conceptualization and methodology for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Urrútia and Bonfill, 2010).

Formulation of the problem

To formulate the problem, we used the PICOS protocol (Participants, Intervention, Comparisons, Outcomes and Study design) by the PRISMA Group (2009). This systematic search was conducted to identify works concerning the following questions: What are the characteristics of adult people (P) who were adopted during their childhood (I), using post-adoption resources; what are their needs, and what answers do they receive (O), according to studies with quantitative or qualitative designs and intervention programs (S)? In this case, comparisons (C) are omitted because they are not needed according to the aims of this paper.

Search strategy

Studies were identified through electronic databases [WOS, Scopus, ProQuest, Dialnet, PsycARTICLES, PsycINFO, PsicoDoc] and specialized journals (*Adoption & Fostering* and *Adoption Quarterly*). The search was conducted between 2005 and 2018. Considering the regulation of adoption in Spain (Law 21/1987) as a starting point, most of the people who were adopted at that time reached adulthood in 2005. The search terms: “post-adoption”, “post-adoption services”, “post-adoption counselling”, “post-adoption support” and “mental health services AND adoption” cross-linked with “adult”, “adulthood” and “youth”. The decision to use “youth” is based on the inclusion of emerging adults under the definition of the term.

Selection criteria

Papers were considered if they included information about: (1) description of the needs of adult adoptees who use post-adoption resources, (2) those people’s characteristics, or (3) description of post-adoption services or resources. The inclusion criteria were: (i) referring to adults, (ii) domestic or international adoption, and (iii) works published between 2005 and 2018. This review did not focus on works about psychological problems that did not include information about post-adoption resources.

Study selection

First, studies were selected based on their titles and an overview of their abstracts. Second, three independent reviewers read carefully all the abstracts of the selected works (Sánchez-Meca and Botella, 2010; Perestelo-Perez, 2013). Then, reviewers independently screened papers for inclusion. In both phases, discrepancies were discussed and, if an agreement was not reached, the decision was considered by another reviewer. In the last phase, each reviewer fully read the selected articles.

Assessment of bias

Different actions were carried out to prevent bias. First, the search was done in English and in Spanish to avoid language bias, and studies that appeared in other languages were also included (e.g., French). Second, independent reviewers read all the abstracts and articles and made decisions together. Finally, a quality of evidence score was assigned to every work according to the Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (2015). Scores ranged from 1 to 4 (1. Meta-analyses and systematic reviews; 2. Case control and cohort studies; 3. Non-analytic studies; and 4. Experts' opinions). Additionally, a symbol was added concerning the risk of bias (“-”=high, “+”=low, “++”=very low). See supplementary table.

Results

Included studies

Figure 1 presents the flow diagram of the selection process. Initially, we found 5291 references in the databases and 1336 in the specialized journals. Next, duplicates were deleted, as well as those works unrelated to the topic. Then, after reviewing selection criteria considering titles and an overview of the abstracts, 263 works passed that stage. Once abstracts were reviewed, we selected 53 documents for full-text reading. At that stage, 13 more papers were excluded for not fulfilling the selection criteria. Finally, 40 works were selected.

Figure 1

As shown in the supplementary table, the included works used different methodologies; 16 of them were qualitative and 11 were quantitative. In addition, some studies used mixed methods ($n=4$), descriptive information ($n=5$), literature reviews ($n=2$), systematic review ($n=1$), and meta-analysis ($n=1$). Most of the samples included between 20 and 200 participants, but they ranged from 6 to 3427. Not all participants were adoptees; some samples consisted of adoption professionals, and others added a comparison group. Most studies included a wide age range (12 – 98 years), but many of them (25%) were focused on

early adulthood (18 – 40 years). About half of the documents were from the USA but some were from Australia, UK, Spain or other European countries.

Analysis and Synthesis

The content of the included papers has been organised into three sections (supplementary figure).

Needs of adult adoptees

According to the reviewed literature, adult adoptees show a wide range of demands or needs for post-adoption services. This section has been divided into four blocks (supplementary figure).

Contact/Reunion with birth family. One of the most frequent needs that adult adoptees express is the search for origins, seeking information about their birth families or trying to contact them (Passmore *et al.*, 2005; Löwstedt, 2007; Ortiz and Rosso, 2007; Ayers-Lopez *et al.*, 2008; Passmore and Chipuer, 2009; Curtis and Pearson, 2010; Rosset *et al.*, 2013; Harris, 2014a; Docan-Morgan, 2016; Greenhow *et al.*, 2016; O’Neill *et al.*, 2016). Although some adoptees prefer searching independently, using internet or social media (Greenhow *et al.*, 2016), others do so through post-adoption services, requiring information about their birth families and asking for help to establish and maintain contact (Ortiz and Rosso, 2007). Some reasons for seeking their birth families are: solving personal issues (Passmore *et al.*, 2006), medical concerns (Curtis and Pearson, 2010; Rosset *et al.*, 2013), genetic matters (Rosset *et al.*, 2013), ethnic identity development (Harris, 2014a; Docan-Morgan, 2016) or because they suffered abuse from the adoptive family (Harris, 2014b).

Ethnic identity development and connection to birth culture. Some studies have highlighted adult adoptees’ need to develop ethnic identity (Patel, 2007; Ferrell, 2017; Moore, 2017; Dandridge, 2018). Most inter-country adoptees identify with their birth country (Docan-Morgan, 2016). For them, it is necessary to explore several issues related to

identity and its role in their lives to develop a strong support system (Ferrell, 2017). Moore (2017) remarked on the importance of understanding the multiple facets of identity development, and families' responsibility in this process. Reynolds (2016) showed the importance of the adoptive name for identity development. Likewise, Dandridge (2017) reported the need for providing support and socialization practices, both for families and adoptees. These support services are especially important for transracial adoptees, because of their complex transition to adulthood (Scarvelis *et al.*, 2017). Harris (2014a) identified some support needs that adoptees consider unmet by adoption services during their childhood, which are still present: racism, language and culture, meeting other adult transracial adoptees, and receiving counselling and psychotherapy regardless of their race.

Mental health and psychosocial adjustment. Several works acknowledged adult adoptees' support-seeking for their mental health or psychosocial adjustment (Pearson *et al.*, 2007; Beine *et al.*, 2008; Behle and Pinguart, 2016; Melero and Sánchez-Sandoval, 2017). Some studies identified a higher prevalence of psychological difficulties among adopted people (Beine *et al.*, 2008; Behle and Pinguart, 2016), so the need for resources and support in this population is higher. During adolescence, adoptees seek counselling for identity-related matters, but in adulthood, they look for help when they are starting a new family or when they have questions about their background (Kreishner, 2002, cited by Pearson *et al.*, 2007). In this line, disorders that lead to support-seeking might also vary as a function of age (Beine *et al.*, 2008).

Improvement of relationships with adoptive family. Only one work (Passmore *et al.*, 2005) mentioned some need related to adults' difficulties with their adoptive families. In this case, they raised the need for counselling to strengthen family relations and prevent problems. According to Harris (2014b), there is a need for support in adoptees who suffered abuse in their adoptive families.

Characteristics of applicants of post-adoption services.

The second aim was to study the characteristics of adult adoptees who use post-adoption resources. However, there was little information about this. Two main points emerged when looking for these characteristics: people seeking their origins and needing mental health services.

Concerning applicants seeking their origins, research highlights that adult adoptees who use post-adoption resources are a heterogeneous group (Passmore *et al.*, 2005; Sonuga-Barke *et al.*, 2017). Their reasons to start searching are varied (Passmore *et al.*, 2005). Not every search is due to discomfort with the adoptive families (Löwstedt, 2007). On the contrary, search often coincides with transition periods, generally including important life events (marriage, parenthood, important losses). In relation to sociodemographic aspects, although they normally reach services after majority (Ortiz and Rosso, 2007), the age range is wide. According to O'Neill *et al.*, (2016), adults reunited with their birth siblings were between 20 and 70 years old. Studies showed more females searching for their origins (Curtis and Pearson, 2010; O'Neill *et al.*, 2016).

Secondly, regarding people who demand mental health services, it was impossible to identify a unique profile. Concerning sociodemographic characteristics, the age range was broad (e.g., 22-98 years, mean of 43.2 in Pearson *et al.*, 2007), with a higher prevalence of females (Laubjerg and Petersson, 2011, cited by Melero and Sánchez-Sandoval, 2017; Pearson *et al.*, 2007). Concerning the manifested disorders, in their meta-analysis, Behle and Pinquart (2016) showed that adoptees' risk of psychiatric diagnosis, treatment and hospitalization is nearly twice as high as that of non-adoptees. Concretely, adoptees have a higher risk for ADHD, anxiety, substance use, depression, personality disorders and psychosis. In case of clinical diagnosis, adoptees and their families are as willing as other people to seek treatment. Adult adoptees who have psychotic disorders are at higher risk of

being admitted as psychiatric inpatients (Beine *et al.*, 2008). However, Laubjerg and Petersson (2010, cited by Melero and Sánchez-Sandoval, 2017) highlighted that being adopted *per se* does not increase the risk for inpatient psychiatric contact.

Harris (2014a) reported that some applicants for post-adoption services suffered physical, sexual or emotional abuse by the adoptive family, or adoption breakdown. Some of these adoptees became regular users of mental health services, and others sought help through counselling, psychotherapy and support groups (Harris, 2014b).

Resources.

The last aim was to describe and organise post-adoption resources for adult adoptees. This section is the longest because previous literature provides more information about this topic. Findings have been grouped into five subsections (supplementary figure).

Post-adoption services. Post-adoption services are intended mainly to guide adoptive families to ease their adopted children's adjustment. However, various works emphasised the need for providing post-adoption services to adults. Docan-Morgan (2016) suggested that the need for support services still exists during adulthood. On another hand, Harris (2014a) stated that there is no full adoption support system in her country to cover the needs both of adults and children. Finally, Patel (2007) highlighted the need to establish a specific support system for transracial adoptees to provide counselling to cope with their unique difficulties.

Undoubtedly, a frequent service for adults is the search for origins. Löwstedt (2007) mentioned a Swedish service called "*Journeys and roots*", that becomes part of their search process and facilitates counselling for long periods of time. Rosset *et al.* (2013) described another service of search for origins offered in Paris since 2006. The team is responsible for psychological support, accompaniment and counselling to discover adoptees' origins. The process normally takes around two years, starting with the demand and finishing in the reunion with the birth family.

In Spain, Ortiz and Rosso (2007) presented a post-adoption service, ongoing since 2001. Although it is not specific for adults, its main purpose is to improve parent-child relationships and to support the resolution of difficulties after adoption. This service addresses four main areas: counselling, family/individual therapy training, and counselling and mediation in the search process.

Intervention programs. In addition to post-adoption services, the analysis revealed specific programs offered to adult adoptees or professionals working with them.

Search for origins program (Ortiz and Rosso, 2007). This post-adoption service offers a specific program oriented toward the search for origins that starts with a psychosocial assessment including motivations, social and personal resources, family support, etc. Specifically, the program has three main stages: to get to know their personal stories, exchange information with the birth family, and contact with the birth family. This program helps the reconstruction of birth families through support and follow-ups.

Attachment-based program "LEARN" (Baim and Morrison, 2011). It is based mainly on interviews about attachment. The program helps users to recover and review their life-stories. It includes five stages: (a) Listening to the stories and recognising indicators, (b) Analysing and clarifying the stories, (c) Accessing and integrating hidden parts, (d) Reviewing the stories and creating a reflective assimilation of the process, (e) Naming the process.

Training for adoption competency (TAC). This program trains professionals in adoption issues. It includes the main competencies and the necessary abilities concerning adoption (Atkinson and Riley, 2017). Most of the participants are social workers, but there are also counsellors, therapists and mental health professionals (Atkinson *et al.*, 2013). The program has four components (Atkinson and Riley, 2017): (a) 12 units with a final applied project, (b)

6-month consultation in clinical practice, (c) a trainer credentialing and support process, (d) an ongoing multicomponent evaluation.

Support groups. Support groups are the post-adoption service resource most frequently offered by private agencies (Mack, 2006). In the last decade, some groups emerged through social media, focusing on adoptees' experiences. For instance, Facebook allowed the creation of pages like "*Lost Daughters Facebook*" (Grotevant, cited by Wiley, 2017). Harris (2014a) found that five out of seven interviewed adoptees said they were likely to attend a support group for transracial adoptees. In fact, several adoption agencies created groups for them, even offering workshops for birth families searchers. The regional adoption consortia offer the opportunity to create services for transracial adoptees, where they can share resources, abilities and knowledge. Cox and Lieberthal (2005) noted the growing number of organizations created by adult adoptees: some for social issues and others with a more political or ideological approach related to adoption.

Nowadays, other activities might be considered somehow specially organised by support groups, for instance, cultural events for adoptees to look into their birth culture. Scarvelis *et al.* (2017) described some practices from Australia, especially attendance at festivals and events related to birth cultures, both for adoptees and their adoptive families. On another hand, Godon *et al.* (2014) found that some adoptees joined ethnic groups to help them with identity development. Those groups provided a sense of belonging and an opportunity to connect with their birth communities. Tieman *et al.* (2008) (cited by Godon *et al.*, 2014) stated that transracial adult adoptees who grew up in predominantly white US communities had access to cultural camps and other activities, giving them the opportunity to explore and resolve issues about growing up as minorities. One of their proposals is the provision of language abilities, cultural information and opportunities to travel to birth

countries. These experiences are considered better than short-term cultural experiences and cultural camps.

Other resources nonspecific for adoptees. There are other services that, although they are not specific for adoptees, might be used by them, for example, mental health services or Alcoholics Anonymous (Pearson *et al.*, 2007). Melero and Sánchez-Sandoval (2017) highlighted the existence of some programs related to mental health for young adults having problems with the law or substance abuse, in which adoptees are overrepresented. Dekker *et al.* (2017) reported that, in the Netherlands, adoptees depend on regular mental health services. If they need specialized services, they can request the Dutch Foundation Adoption Services, which has a register of adoption specialized professionals.

Regarding access to mental health services, Wall (2011) found that 56.8% of the participants in his study received these services, either as children or adults. However, according to Atkinson *et al.* (2013), it is important to examine adoptees' experiences with mental health professionals. These authors asked adoptees and their parents about their experiences visiting mental health professionals, finding that: 24.87% thought that professionals were suitable for adoption issues, 26.18% disagreed, and 48.95% informed that some were suitable and some were not. Many adoptees said that they spent a long time searching for a competent therapist. Similarly, 82% of the respondents stated that they would select a certified professional who was competent in adoption matters.

Recommendations for professionals. Several studies have identified the need for competent professionals in adoption issues (Pearson *et al.*, 2007; Harrison, 2017; Wiley, 2017). One of the main recommendations for professionals is to receive training in adoption matters (Passmore and Feeney, 2009). Being involved in programs like TAC (Graham *et al.*, 2015) improves assessments and practice of clinicians and increases the quality and effectiveness of their services (Atkinson and Riley, 2017). Other ways are, for example, peer

support groups or professional organizations. Some of the issues in which professionals must improve their competency are: the uniqueness of adoption, health, family, adoptees' identity, searching process, adoption policies and post-adoption services (Pearson *et al.*, 2007; Harrison, 2017).

Concerning search for origins, some recommendations for those professionals who work with adult adoptees highlight the importance of helping them to analyse the reasons for searching (Passmore *et al.*, 2006), to create realistic expectations about reunion with birth families (Passmore *et al.*, 2006; Passmore and Feeney, 2009; Curtis and Pearson, 2010) and to prepare them for different types of reunion (Passmore *et al.*, 2005; Passmore and Chipuer, 2009).

Nonetheless, Passmore *et al.* (2006) remarked that counsellors must be aware of adoptees' heterogeneity, instead of considering them as identical. This implies offering different kinds of help depending on adoptees' needs. In line with this, some professionals recommend indirect contact, through virtual resources, instead of direct contact (Greenhow *et al.*, 2016). Curtis and Pearson (2010) advised that, in addition to helping in the search and reunion process, professionals should provide support groups and work with the whole adoption triad. They also recommend professionals to focus on all stages of the searching process and the related psychological problems. According to O'Neill *et al.* (2016), adult adoptees are recommended to have follow-up meetings with social workers and to use support groups for reunited people.

Researchers recommend counsellors to work with the identity process. First, they must be aware of identity development to understand adoptees and their families (Ferrell, 2017). Second, counsellors must understand the links between search and identity, and help people with diffuse identity to improve their decision making (Passmore *et al.*, 2005). Specifically concerning transracial adoptions, professionals must highlight the culture from which the

adoptive parent (Moore, 2017) and understand adoptees' needs in order to offer them sensitive practices and resources (Baden, 2007; Dandridge, 2018). Some of these resources are mentoring programs, assisting families to understand the culture (Dandridge, 2018), helping adoptees to identify with their birth cultures, participation in cultural activities, and economic support to know the birth culture (Haenga-Collins, 2015). Other recommendations are: using a systemic approach (Moore, 2017), reading books about transracial adoption (Reynolds, 2016), or recognizing the consequences of double loss in decision making for transracial adoptees (Cox and Lieberthal, 2005).

It is also important to consider some peculiarities, such as single-parent adoptions. According to Pakizegi (2007), some clinical implications for this adoptions are: supporting the independence of the adoptee to maintain the connection with the adoptive parent, evaluating guilt caused by independence, considering intimacy issues and becoming birth parents themselves, and supporting the searching process.

Finally, some studies made recommendations to work with other members of the adoption triad. Referring to adoptive families, providing parents with information about family dynamics might help them to be prepared for and to prepare adoptees to cope with developmental tasks and autonomy in their own context (Wall, 2012). Adoptive families might be struggling due to the contact of their children with their birth families (Passmore and Chipuer, 2009), so it is also important to assess issues with that contact (Pakizegi, 2007). For transracial adoptions, practitioners should address the cultural socialization within the family context, which is important for adoptees' identity development (Moore, 2017).

There are also some recommendations for practice with birth families. The first refers to the information about birth fathers, which sometimes is only available through the birth mother, who might have been abandoned by the father. Consequently, counsellors might help birth mothers to recover from this issue (Passmore and Feeney, 2009). Other

recommendations are to assist birth parents to use adoption registries if they want to contact their children (Ayers-Lopez *et al.*, 2008) and to work with birth fathers' expectations about the relationship with their adult children (Passmore and Chipuer, 2009).

Conclusions and Discussion

This review is unique in its examination of adult adoptees' needs and the resources they are offered. Although post-adoption resources are mainly oriented to the first years after adoption, they might be necessary during the whole lifespan. The child's arrival involves a reorganization of the family. Later, during childhood, feelings of loss emerge, and adolescence brings new challenges to be faced. Finally, other tasks appear with adulthood (Arnett, 2004; Brodzinsky *et al.*, 2014). These issues lead us to wonder whether it is necessary to offer post-adoption resources also during adulthood, as other authors propose (Docan-Morgan, 2016; Scarvelis *et al.*, 2017). The main purpose of this review was, indeed, to know adult adoptees' demands and the resources offered to them.

Included studies reflect the work of researchers and professionals from different cultural backgrounds (Australia, Belgium, Germany, France, India, Ireland, The Netherlands, New Zealand, UK, Spain, Sweden and USA). Despite the diverse cultural settings, it was possible to identify common needs and shared answers. Together with the global vision provided, results of this review also highlight the need for diffusion of other intervention strategies that are probably being used in other countries.

The first notable finding is the description of the post-adoption services that are offered in different countries. These are normally offered to children, adolescents and their families. According to Scarvelis *et al.* (2017), these services should not be optional for adults, because transitioning to adulthood implies the need for continuous support. In relation to our first aim, studies showed mainly three needs among adult adoptees: contact or reunion with birth family, ethnic identity development and connection to birth culture, and psychological

support. The first two were the most common ones. The development of ethnic identity has been recognised as crucial during emerging adulthood, and is a protective factor for adoptees' well-being (Ferrari *et al.*, 2015).

The analysed works barely mentioned the adoptees' demand for improving adoptive family relationships. These results could be interpreted as an indicator of adoption success, assessed through the quality of family dynamics. Longitudinal researches show the high level of satisfaction both of adoptive parents and children with adoption (Sánchez-Sandoval, 2011). In fact, most people who start searching do not have poor relationships with their adoptive parents, but are trying to increase their sense of identity (Sachdev, 1992, cited by Amorós *et al.*, 1998). However, this does not preclude the need of some adoptees to perform an internal search and personal development in relation to identity, and an external search about their origins or culture. Achieving an autonomous life and creating families are the main reasons for adoptees to start searching (Grau Quintana, 2017).

Regarding the characteristics of adult adoptees who demand post-adoption resources, we conclude that they are a heterogeneous group, both in personal and in other aspects, for instance, in the reasons for searching. Whereas in studies with children and adolescents, there are some risk factors (e.g. late adoptions, adverse childhood experiences) associated with higher difficulties and needs, this review does not allow the identification of personal or social variables associated with the related demands in adulthood, except for finding a higher number of female than male searchers (Curtis and Pearson, 2010; O'Neill *et al.*, 2016). Concerning early experiences, adversity in childhood do not directly determine adult adjustment. Longitudinal studies with adopted women conclude that most of them address later difficulties effectively, if orphanage care was followed by a good quality adoption (Grant and Rushton, 2018). Not even childhood difficulties in adoptees predict well-being in adulthood, there are other important variables that influence, such as social support (Sánchez-

Sandoval *et al.*, 2019). This might be one of the reasons that hinder the creation of profiles considering the previous characteristics.

This review also found few structured programs for adults focused on different important adoption issues: search for origins (Ortiz and Rosso, 2007), attachment development (Baim and Morrison, 2011) and professionals' training in adoption issues (Atkinson *et al.*, 2013; Atkinson and Riley, 2017). In addition, some specific tools such as support groups are the most frequent resource offered by private agencies. However, there are other resources more oriented to international adoptees, such as cultural events that attempt to connect adoptees and their birth cultures (Godon *et al.*, 2014; Scarvelis *et al.*, 2017). Finally, adoptees also have access to other resources that were not specifically designed for them, like mental health services (Dekker *et al.*, 2017) or treatment for drug users (Pearson *et al.*, 2007).

Beyond concrete resources, several works insist on the need for training in adoption issues for professionals who work with adoptees. Professional training might help them to be more sensitive to adopted patients' concerns (Oke *et al.*, 2015). Nonetheless, certificate programs in adoption competence are expensive, so universities and agencies should make the appropriate changes to offer an adequate service to the members of the adoption triad (Harrison, 2017).

Other recommendations for professionals refer to the health and well-being of adopted people. Adoption issues are not the only reason for adoptees to visit a professional. Nonetheless, it is important for professionals to be aware of issues such as early adversity and histories of deprivation (Sonuga-Barke *et al.*, 2017), attachment, disclosure of adoption, stigma, integration in the family, and reasons for and against searching (Gonsalves, 2016). According to Gonsalves (2016), this might help adoptees to understand their adoption and loss. Some adoptees might suffer distress when using mental health services, so adoption

professionals must be trained in histories of abuse, laws, therapy, support groups and connection with others (Harris, 2014b). Support groups, in this case, might be a safe context for adoptees to talk about their experiences and feelings without considering them from a pathological view (Oke *et al.*, 2015).

One of the conclusions of this review is that adult adoptees mainly receive individualized answers. There are few interventions with a more contextual perspective, including adoptive and birth families. The work is mostly oriented towards the adopted person. Our recommendation is to include other people as intervention targets, for instance, partners or children. In this line, it is recommended to develop programs for the general population to combat stereotypes about adopted people.

Taking everything into account, it is important to consider the relation between research and practice, because it is difficult to know whether those recommendations are known by professionals working in the field. It might be appropriate to create more structured resources connecting practice and research. This would ease professionals' work and make more relevant research contributions to our society.

Limitations

Some limitations of this study need to be considered. One limitation is the heterogeneity of the studies. It was difficult to organise and synthesize works with different characteristics, methodologies and publication formats. Despite that, it allowed us to provide a fuller picture of the topic.

Another limitation is about the search for publications. It was limited to scientific databases and the main journals on adoption matters. However, there may be national programs that are unpublished. Access to these documents is difficult, and this involves a loss

of information about practices that are currently being applied concerning post-adoption resources.

Finally, it should be considered that most of the works included general recommendations related to research results. It is very difficult to know whether such recommendations are reaching professionals and whether they are being applied to clinical practice. All in all, we propose the creation of resources that consider those recommendations to make their application easier for professionals who are directly involved in adoption.

Future implications

Currently, most of the demands refer to search and contact with the birth family. At the same time, new demands might appear in the near future, arising from other adoption types; for instance, open adoptions where adoptees maintain some contact with their birth families.

More research is needed on adult adoptees' mental health and well-being and, in general, on people who experienced early adversity and attended to the Child Welfare System. That kind of research will allow us to know whether living in an adoptive family promotes the recovery from the impact of those experiences or whether it persists over time. Similarly, future research with adult adoptees will enable us to know whether transitioning to adulthood implies the emergence of new demands in this group. Those results would also allow the creation of post-adoption resources that more effectively match the concrete needs of adult adoptees.

Many works included general recommendations or targeted interventions without the required assessment of their results. It is necessary for intervention programs in the Child Welfare System to be evidence-based. The current challenge is to guarantee that professional interventions and other initiatives meet the international quality standards for psychoeducational programs.

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Figure legend

Figure 1. Flow diagram. Selection process of the included works in the systematic review.

40 studies completed the process and were included.

Supplementary figure. Organization of findings. Several information was found, so it was organized for a better understanding. Findings were divided into three different sections.

Supplementary table.

Included studies and their characteristics.

Study/Country	Sample	Age	Measures	Design	Services information	Quality of evidence
(Passmore & Chipuer, 2009)/ Australia	17 women who had been adopted prior to 2 years of age.	30-47	Interview	Qualitative	- Search for origins. - Recommendations for professionals.	3
(Pearson, Curtis, & Chapman, 2007)/ USA	156 adults (135 female and 21 male)	22-89	Survey: Demographic/general adoption information and 20 questions about psychological issues	Quantitative	- Need for support. - Women seek help more than men. - Other services to use. - Formation of professionals. - Recommendations for professionals.	2+
(Passmore, Fogarty, Bourke & Baker-Evans, 2005)/ USA	66 female and 34 male adoptees	18-70	Rosenberg Self-Esteem SES, ISI3, PBI	Quantitative	- Search for origins. - Heterogeneity. - Problems with adoptive families. - Recommendations for professionals.	2+
(Löwstedt, 2007)/ Sweden	NP	NP	NP	Description of services	- Search for origins. - “ <i>Journeys and roots</i> ” service	4
(Ortiz & Rosso, 2007)/ Spain	NP	NP	NP	Description of services	- Search for origins program (more frequent in domestic adoption). - Description of post-adoption services.	4
(Wiley, 2017)/ USA	NP	NP	NP	Literature review	- Need for professionals’ formation. - Social media tools. - Lack of access to some information.	3
(Moore, 2017)/ USA	256 transracial adoptees (70.3% female)	18-54	Demographic questionnaire, DSI-SF, ERSTAS, Belongingness and Ethnic Self-Perception scale, PANAS	Quantitative	- Ethnic identity development. - Recommendations for professionals.	2+
(Ferrell, 2017)/ USA	149 international adult adoptees (37.6% female)	18-29	MEIM- R, BFRS, PEDQ-CV, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale	Quantitative	- Need for ethnic identity development. - Recommendations for professionals.	2+

(Scarvelis, Crisp, & Goldingay, 2017)/ Australia	12 international adult adoptees (9 male, 3 female)	From early 20s to early 30s	Interview	Qualitative	- Need for support connecting with origins. - Cultural events. - Lack of services for adults.	3
(O'Neill, Mcauley, & Loughran, 2016)/ Ireland	33 adult adoptees (8 males, 25 females)	20-70	Interview	Qualitative	- Search for the origins and reunion. - Recommendations for professionals.	3
(Greenhow, Hackett, Jones, & Meins, 2016)/ UK	11 adoptive parents and 6 adopted young people	14-22	Semi-structured interview	Qualitative	- Search for the origins need. - Recommendations for professionals.	3
(Ayers-Lopez, Henney, McRoy, Hanna, & Grotevant, 2008)/ USA	127 birthmothers (9% adopted)	26-54	Semi-structured interview	Qualitative	- Search for origins. - Recommendations for adoptees.	3
(Gonsalves, 2016)/ USA	9 adult adoptees	25-65	Interview	Qualitative	- Recommendations for professionals.	3
(Dandridge, 2017)/ USA	118 transracial adult adoptees (62.2% female)	18-70	Demographic survey, MPD, MEIM.	Quantitative (cross-sectional)	- Ethnic identity development. - Recommendations for professionals.	2+
(Melero, & Sánchez-Sandoval, 2017)/ Spain	NP	NP	NP	Systematic Review	- Recommendations for professionals.	1+
(Sounga-Barke et al., 2017)/ UK	165 Romanian and 52 UK adoptees	22-25	Revised Rutter scale at ages 6 and 11 years; SDQ at age 15; and Conners' Comprehensive Behavior Rating Scale, Social Communication Questionnaire, McCarthy Scales, WISC and WAIS.	Quantitative (longitudinal)	- Heterogeneous clinical picture. - Recommendations for professionals.	2+
(Dekker, Tieman, Vinke, van der Ende, Verhulst, & Juffer,	75 adult domestic adoptees, 2021	19-30	Interview ASR, interview	Quantitative (Cross-sectional)	- No differences in aftercare. - Mental health services.	2++

2017)/The Netherlands	non-adoptees, 1331 international adoptees					- Adoption specialized professionals registry.	
(Javier, Baden , Biafora , & Camacho-Gingerich, 2007)/USA	NP	NP	NP	Mixed methods		- Implications for practitioners.	3
(Baim & Morrison, 2011)/ UK	NP	NP	NP	Description of program		- LEARN model of attachment-based interviewing.	3
(Wall, 2011)/USA	88 adult adoptees (76 female)	18-75	FACES-IV, SPWB, Demographic questionnaire.	Quantitative		- 56.8% mental health services. - Recommendations for professionals.	2+
(Mack, 2006)/USA	95 post-adoption agencies	NP	Survey	Qualitative		- Services offered by post-adoption agencies	3
(Graham, Alexander, Koch, & Wall, 2015)/USA	NP	NP	NP	Description of assessment		- TAC program.	3
(Atkinson & Riley, 2017)/USA	885 professionals	NP	Observation, self-ratings	Qualitative		- Assessment of TAC program. - Recommendations for professionals.	3
(Harrison, 2017)/USA	8 adult adoptees	45-60	Interview	Qualitative		- Formation of professionals (need and program). - Recommendations for professionals.	3
(Reynolds, 2016)/USA	19 transracial Korean American adoptees (12 female)	22-43	Interview	Qualitative		- Recommendations for professionals. - Ethnic identity development.	3
(Beine, Constant, & Goffinet, 2008)/Belgium	148 hospitalized patients (11.5% adoptees)	12-20	DSM diagnostic criteria, sociodemographic data	Quantitative		- Percentage of adoptive patients 5-10 times superior to general population. - Adult group: more frequent psychotic disorders.	2+
(Docan-Morgan, 2016)/USA	19 Korean adoptees	18-38	Interview	Qualitative		- Need for appropriate services for adoptees. - Reunion with birth family.	3
(Behle & Pinguart, 2016)/Germany	Adoptees vs. non-adoptees	NP	NP	Meta-analysis		- Most common psychiatric diagnoses. - Overrepresentation.	1++

(Atkinson, Gonet, Freundlich, & Riley, 2013)/USA	185 TAC participants	NP	Online survey	Qualitative	- Formation of professionals. - Mental health practice.	3
(Harris, 2014a)/UK	12 transracially adopted adults	19-33	Interview and focus groups	Qualitative	- Contact with birth family. - Need for support. - Family situation. - Support groups. - Lack of appropriate services. - Recommendations for practice.	3
(Harris, 2014b)/UK	66 (23 adoptees, rest birth and adoptive family)	Adults (age range not mentioned)	Interview and focus groups	Qualitative	- Support in searching for the birth family. - Family situation. - Recommendations for professionals.	3
(Oke, Groza, Park, Kalyanvala, & Shetty, 2005)/India	46 adopted adults	20-30	Interview, SF-36, BSD.	Quantitative	- Neglect and psychological issues. - Implications for practice.	2+
(Curts & Pearson, 2010)/USA	130 adult adoptees (112 female)	23-98	Survey about demographic/general adoption information and questions about psychological issues.	Mixed methods	- Search for birth family (need and service). - More women. - Recommendations for professionals.	2+
(Rosset, 2013)/France	NP	NP	NP	Description of services	- Needs: search for origins and identity development. - Search for origins service. - Description of services.	4
(Cox & Lieberthal, 2005)/USA	NP	NP	NP	Literature review	- Creation of groups. - Recommendations for professionals.	3
(Patel, 2007)/UK	6 transracially adopted adults	21-43	Interview	Qualitative	- Lack of appropriate services.	3
(Haenga-Collins & Gibbs, 2015)/New Zealand to Europe	6 Maori adopted adults	(born from late 50s to early 70s)	Interview	Qualitative	- Recommendations for professionals working in transcultural adoption.	3
(Passmore & Feeney, 2009)/Australia	18 adult adoptees (15 females)	27-60	Survey	Mixed methods (focus on qualitative)	- Implications for counseling.	3
(Godon, Green, & Ramsey, 2014)/USA	109 transracial adoptees (75.2% female)	18-37	Survey and interview, MEIM, RSE.	Mixed methods (cross-sectional)	- Cultural events.	2+

(Passmore, Feeney, Peterson, & Shimmaki, 2006)/Australia	144 adoptees, 131 non-adoptees	18-70	Demographic questionnaire, DASS-D, Scale of Emotional Arousal, PBI, PSI, MSQ	Quantitative	- Recommendations for professionals. - Search for origins.	2+
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Note. ASR = Adult Self-Report. BFRS = Brief Family Relationship Scale. BSD = Brief Screen for Depression. DASS-D = Depression Anxiety Stress Scales. DSI-SF = Differentiation of Self Inventory – Short Form. ERSTAS = Ethnic and Racial Socialization of Transracial Adoptee Scale. FACES = Family Adaptability and Cohesion Evaluation Scales. ISI3 = Identity Style Inventory. MEIM = Multi Ethnic Identity Measure. MEIM- R = Multi Ethnic Identity Model Revised. MPD = Measures of Psychosocial Development. MSQ = Motives for Searching Questionnaire. PANAS = Positive Affect and Negative Affect Scale. PBI = Parental Bonding Instrument. PEDQ-CV = Perceived Ethnic Discrimination Questionnaire Community Version. PSI = Parental Style Index. RSE = Rosenberg Self-Esteem. SDQ = Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire. SES = Self-Esteem Scale. SF-36 = Health Survey Short Forms. SPWB = Scales of Psychological Well-Being. TAC = Training for Adoption Competency. WAIS = Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence in Adulthood. WISC = Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children.